

Benefit Management for ERP systems

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Abstract: Companies around the world spend sometimes many millions for the implementation of ERP-systems (Enterprise Resource Planning systems are used by big organizations and companies for integrated business operation in finance, logistics and human resources) in projects lasting over several years. Nevertheless many of these systems do not deliver the expected benefits. Especially after going live, which is the beginning of the postimplementation phase, in most cases a performance drop can be observed, which lasts for months.

There is a special research area in literature known as „benefit management”, which deals with this problem. Despite comprehensive theoretical concepts benefit management is not common in practice so that the problem of benefits realisation persists even 30 years after the introduction of ERP systems to the market.

The goal of this thesis is to investigate the benefits realisation for ERP-systems after going live (postimplementation phase) in the real world based on the Mixed Methods Approach.

In the qualitative part of the study 44 end users from four industrial companies and ERP consultants were interviewed to find out how benefits materialize, how benefits can be measured and quantified by means of key performance indicators (KPI) and how benefits can be realised over the entire life cycle. These interviews were evaluated using the Qualitative Contents Analysis of Mayring.

In the quantitative part of the study a set of 12 KPIs (inventory value of raw materials, stock turnover rate of raw materials, cycle time of production orders, cost deviation of production orders, inventory value of finished goods, stock turnover rate of finished goods, lead time of customer orders, delivery reliability, percentage of customer orders delivered in time, duration of monthly financial closing, number of IT tickets and system usage), which were downloaded as monthly measurement values directly from ERP-systems, was analysed for four participating case study companies over a period of 24 months after going live using SPSS software for statistical evaluations.

The result shows that the implementation of an ERP-system is not finished with going live, but requires permanent efforts for benefits realisation to optimize and adjust business processes, provide ongoing end user trainings and further development of an ERP-system in order to exploit the benefit potential of an ERP-system during the whole lifecycle in the best way.

The results of the study show the time dependence of the KPIs and that they can be improved by certain measures. Therefor the author proposes a concept for a benefit controlling to support benefits realisation over the entire life cycle of an ERP-system based on a regular evaluation of a set of processual KPIs.

Keywords: Benefit Management, Benefit Controlling, Benefit realisation, ERP-systems, ERP postimplementation, longitudinal measurement

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

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1 Introduction

The success of IT-projects and the realisation of benefits after implementation are an old and still actual problem.

A study of the Standish-Group shows, that two third of all IT-Projects do not reach the planned targets. The portion of failed IT-Projects stays on this level since many years and does not decrease [Nelson, 07].

Even if an IT-project is completed in the planned time frame and within the budget, this does not necessarily mean that it creates benefits. Coombs states, that it requires more than to meet the criterions of the Magic Triangle to make a project successful [Coombs, 14]:

“... if investments in information systems and information technology are to be considered successful then they have to achieve more than technical targets such as satisfying a project's budget, time scale and feature requirements.”

According to a British study around 75 % of all IT-Projects do not deliver the expected benefit [Ward, 07].

Measurements of the benefits are carried out only for 15 % of all analysed IT-projects [Blumberg, 12].

Benefits are harvested rarely with the going live of a new IT system. Even worse a time lag in the order of several months or years can be observed until benefits materialize. In literature only few authors cover the time lag in benefits realisation and even less measured it. This is especially true for complex IT-systems like ERP systems.

Schryen states in a comprehensive literature review that delay effects can last for several years until investments in IT bear fruits. Analysis of productivity do not take into account these delays and can serve as explanation of the Brynjolfsson productivity paradox [Schryen, 10].

Atkinson writes that the effect of an ERP systems on customers can be measured a few weeks after going live, on business success in one to two years after going live and on future fitness in four to five years after going live [Atkinson, 99].

This is especially true for ERP systems, as benefits are based not only on the system itself but depends on many different factors according to Shang / Seddon [Shang, 02]. They evaluated the perceived net benefit flow for different dimensions of benefits based on interviews in four organisations for three years (fig. 1).

Figure 1: Perceived benefits realisation over time (Shang / Seddon)

Generally they noticed an initial deterioration of benefits before benefits rise. The reasons for the time lag are initial problems, faulty data, problems with new business processes, insufficient end user training and lack of acceptance of the new system. Generally operational benefits are realised sooner than strategic benefits. The dotted line shows benefits in the finance applications, which rise faster to a higher benefit level. The shortcoming of this study is that benefits were not really measured but only derived from the perception of senior managers in interviews two years and three years after going live.

McAfee from the Harvard Business School is the first to publish a longitudinal study with detailed measurement of order lead time (time between receipt of a customer order and its shipment) over time at an US computer manufacturer. Order lead time was measured for the last 90 working days in old system and for the first 250 days in the new ERP system separated by a vertical line, which marks the going live of the new ERP system as shown in fig. 2. This figure also shows that average lead time is shorter from the beginning of using the new ERP system, followed by a learning curve with substantial shorter lead times at the end of the 250 days period. The curve also shows high standard deviations at the beginning, which become smaller at the end of the period [McAfee, 02]. Interestingly lead time and standard deviations deteriorate in the last 90 days of using the old legacy systems, which is consistent with findings from earlier research on performance dips. Explanations are that the old system is at its limits and no maintenance is done anymore in the old system.

Figure 2: Average lead time of customer orders over time (McAfee)

In the same case study the percentage of orders shipped late before and after the implementation of the ERP system was measured over 90 days before and 250 days after the going live of the ERP system. Fig. 3 shows the fraction of delayed orders, which is initially higher than in the old system, especially in the first month, followed by a learning curve showing substantial improvement. Again the initially high standard deviation becomes smaller after 120 working days.

Figure 3: Fraction of orders shipped late over time (McAfee)

Cotteleer / Bendoly continue the longitudinal research by extending the period of the longitudinal study to 24 months based also on the order lead time [Cotteleer, 06]. From today's perspective the duration of 24 months is a considerable progress compared to the 250 days in the study of McAfee, as it permits an extended look to time dependency. Fig. 4 shows the results of the study for a period of 12 months with the old system (periods -12 – -1) and the first 24 months with the new ERP system (periods 1 – 24). The diagram shows no values for the last 3 periods in the old system because of proprietary disclosure requests of the company. A substantial improvement of order lead time materializes after 12 months.

Figure 4: Order lead time over a period of 24 months (Cotteleer/Bendoly)

In order to solve the problems of poor and delayed benefits from IT-investments Ward developed the Cranfield Benefits Management Model as a structured approach to plan and realise benefits [Ward, 96]. Recent research on organisational resilience, which covers adaption to new challenges and enhancement of performance over time, shows interesting parallels to benefit management by focusing on digital transformation, learning and training, culture of innovation and value co-creation.

2 Research Method

Literature shows a lack of research in assessing benefits of ERP systems. This is the research gap which shall be filled with the present research, which is based on the mixed method approach.

Creswell describes the three different research methodologies quantitative research, qualitative research and mixed method research with growing interest in qualitative research in the second half of the 20th century. Simultaneously mixed methods evolved [Creswell, 14]. For research work asking questions „how“ and „why“ the use of a qualitative methodology is indicated [Yin, 09].

For qualitative research in IT case studies are frequently applied. Data collection is more open than in quantitative research and can be descriptive, explaining or explorative.

This research work is explorative, as new insights in realising and measuring benefits from applying ERP systems should be gained.

The research is based on the expectation that organisations applying the principles of benefit management will reach a higher benefits level compared to organisations, which do not apply them. The theory of benefit management can be regarded as the basic framework for the present research.

The present research is conducted as a multiple case study, as this permits a literal replication and more robust conclusions according to Yin, especially as considerable differences can be expected in the implementation of ERP-systems [Yin, 09]. Yin points out, that the use of multiple sources of evidence strengthens the construct validity. For this purpose two independent studies were conducted to obtain a deeper insight into benefit realisation and real KPIs from ERP-systems as the data base for the research. The research is based exclusively on ERP systems of the German company SAP as the market leader. ERP products from other software suppliers are not part of this research. The following companies participate in the study:

Company	Industry	No. of employees	Country
A	Automotive	7.500	DE
B	Machine building	800	AT
C	Machine building	700	AT
D	Metal industry	600	AT

Table 1: Participating companies

In the first, qualitative study interviews shall provide better understanding of the benefits realisation process, ways to measure benefits and potential KPIs to quantify benefits.

In the second study a set of selected KPIs is evaluated for companies A – D to measure the change of these KPIs over time in the postimplementation phase (this is the time after the going live of an ERP system). The sequence for the research was to conduct the qualitative research as an explorative study to find out different aspects of benefits realisation and to validate the results by the KPIs of the quantitative study.

2.1 Qualitative Study

44 interviews are conducted in total based on a structured, written interview guide with twelve open ended questions. 28 of these interviews are with key users of the four participating companies and 16 interviews with SAP-consultants. We selected from each company managers from top management, procurement, production, sales, finance, controlling and IT.

The interviews are recorded using the Microsoft Sound Recorder and transcribed for Qualitative Content Analysis by means of MAXQDA Analytics software release 2018. The method of Qualitative Content Analysis by Mayring is applied to find important categories and phrases in the statements of the interviewees, which are classified as codes for analysis. The absolute occurrence of each code and its percentage related to the total number of interviews is calculated and sorted in descending order. The author has done the evaluation also separately for the sample of EPR users and consultants in order to find differences between these two groups.

2.2 Quantitative Study

The quantitative study is carried out as a longitudinal study over a time of 24 months after the going live of an ERP system. In order to avoid that the study lasts also as long the study is conducted ex post based on data stored in the new ERP system. Twelve KPIs are evaluated on a monthly basis for the four industrial companies A – D shown in table 1. Qualitative and quantitative study are done for the same companies to support triangulation. Literature shows time series only for single KPIs like customer order lead time and shorter time frames less than one year. From around 100 companies, which initially were contacted and invited to participate in the research, finally only four companies were willing to participate and share their data. It took more than six months to get the data files with the KPIs from the companies, because internal authorization processes were very time consuming and finalizing nondisclosure agreements and their approval was difficult. This was the hardest obstacle of the study.

These KPIs include inventory value of raw materials, stock turnover rate of raw materials, cycle time of productions orders, cost deviation of production orders, inventory value of finished goods, stock turnover rate of finished goods, lead time of customer orders, delivery reliability, percentage of customer orders delivered in time, duration of monthly financial closing, number of IT tickets and system usage. Initially turnover per employee and Ebit were also proposed for the KPIs, but finally excluded as two companies were not willing to share these data on a monthly basis.

Real live data of the KPIs were downloaded from ERP systems into Microsoft Excel and transferred to IBM SPSS version 25. Time series diagrams were created for

each KPI in SPSS including third-degree polynomial curves and the R^2 cubic value, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for a cubic regression model — i.e. a regression model that includes a cubic (third-degree polynomial) term. The R^2 cubic value is higher than a R^2 quadratic value for all KPIs.

3 Results

The outcome of the research is a comprehensive analysis of benefits realisation for ERP-systems providing the basis for a concept of benefit controlling in chapter 5.

3.1 Qualitative Study

In the following the author presents the results for the 12 questions of the interview guide. For each question the phrases of the answers are classified as codes during the qualitative content analysis in an iterative process. All answers are analysed two or three times regarding new codes. In an additional step, which is not covered by the Methodology of Mayring a quality check of all answers classified under one code is applied to make sure that codes are assigned equally. This paper presents only these codes, which are mentioned by at least 25 % of the interviewees. In the original research each code with the respective percentage is documented for each question in full detail.

Question 1: What is the benefit of an ERP system in general?

Table 2 shows the top codes distilled from the answers of the interviewed persons as absolute number and percentage related to the sample size of 44 interviews.

The most frequently mentioned codes are in line with the following definition of an ERP system showing that the interviewed persons have a clear imagination of the nature of an ERP system: *“An ERP-system is a packaged business solution that is designed to automate and integrate business processes, share common data and practices across the enterprise and provide access to information in real time.”*

Code	Number	Percentage
Map business processes	24	55 %
Integrated software system	20	46 %
Transparency	16	36 %
Unified data base	13	30 %
Efficient execution of processes	13	30 %

Table 2: General aspects of benefit realisation

Question 2: What is the most important benefit of an ERP system for your own area of responsibility?

The second question provides a more specific and personal view based on the experience with an ERP system in the own work area. The codes are related to each other, as the use of a single data base and the integration of the applications contribute to transparency and the quality of the content of the reports in the sense of reliability of the presented figures.

Code	Number	Percentage
Functionality	24	55 %
Map business processes	17	39 %
Single data base	16	36 %
Transparency	16	36 %
Content of reporting	13	30 %
Integration	12	27 %

Table 3: Benefits of ERP system in own field of activity

Question 3: How can you recognize the benefits?

This question is based on question 2 to find out how the interviewees recognize the benefits in their own work area. The codes extracted from the answers are related to each other in the way, that less errors and consistency of processes and data contribute to a higher data quality and transparency.

Code	Number	Percentage
Transparency	16	36 %
Less errors	15	34 %
Data quality	14	32 %
Consistency	14	32 %
Increase of efficiency	14	32 %

Table 4: How can benefits of an ERP system be recognized

Question 4: How would you quantify or measure the benefits?

46 % of the interviewed persons think, that it can be done by means of KPIs supporting the idea of a quantification. 43 % of the respondents think it can be done via the data quality without giving details how this could be implemented. 39 % have no idea how to measure it saying only that it is difficult to measure it. The comparison with the previous legacy system seems reasonable at first sight, but is hardly feasible, as it is no longer available after the implementation of the new ERP system. Functionality and business processes also might be different.

Code	Number	Percentage
KPIs	20	46 %
Data quality	19	43 %
Difficult to measure benefits	17	39 %
Time saving	15	34 %
Increase of efficiency	13	30 %
Process quality	11	25 %
Comparison to former legacy system	11	25 %

Table 5: How can benefits of an ERP system be quantified

A separate evaluation between users and consultants show a significant difference regarding the measurement of benefits. 46 % of the users think that it is difficult to measure benefits but only 25 % of the consultants.

Question 5: Which KPIs are suitable to measure benefits in your opinion?

About 45 different suggestions for KPIs are made like cycle time of production orders, inventory, number of postings per user, days for period end closing, number of IT tickets for any problems with the ERP system, intensity of system usage, time savings for reporting, etc. But only the three KPIs in the table 6 reach our self-defined cut-off percentage of 25 %. Depending on the area of activity of the interviewed person the proposed KPIs were specific for this area of activity, e.g. the head of accounting proposed the duration of monthly financial closing. The KPIs from the quantitative research were also mentioned by the respondents with the following occurrence: cycle time of production orders (23 %), inventory value (23 %), duration of monthly financial closing (21 %), system usage (18 %), lead time of customer orders (14 %), stock turnover rate (9 %) and turnover / employee (7 %).

Code	Number	Percentage
Cycle times of business processes	15	34 %
Delivery reliability	12	28 %
Data quality	11	25 %

Table 6: KPIs for benefits measurement

Question 6: in which time intervals such a measurement could make sense?

This question is important in the light of the longitudinal study and the idea of the benefit controlling proposed in chapter 5. Literature shows that in most cases KPIs are not measured after going live and if they are measured then only once. Further answers are monthly measurement (23 %) and flexible, dependent from the application (16 %). Nearly all interview partners agreed to a regular measurement, which is remarkable, as project management often includes only one evaluation of project outcome after going live and even this single assessment only rarely includes KPIs for benefits.

Code	Number	Percentage
Yearly measurement	19	43 %
Quarterly measurement	13	30 %

Table 7: Periodicity for the measurement of KPIs

Question 7: Which external effects, which have nothing to do with the ERP system itself, could influence these KPIs?

The most important external influence are customers, as a change in buying behaviour changes inventory figures and cycle times, payment behaviour, liquidity and profitability. Market development on second position is considered as an important external influence, as the economic situation, new product trends and changes in legal conditions will impact the level of KPIs. Suppliers are another external influence, e. g.,

if there are shortages in critical components or materials, which increase the cycle times of production orders and lead time of customer orders.

Code	Number	Percentage
Customer behaviour	17	43 %
Market development	14	32 %
Supplier behaviour	13	30 %

Table 8: External influences on the benefits realisation

Question 8: How long did it take after the going live until the new ERP system delivered benefits?

Results are shown in table 9 for at least 20 % occurrence to provide a better picture for the first year of going live. 18 % of the respondents state that benefits are realised starting from the first day after going live. 2 % said that there is no benefit at all from the new ERP system. The time of several months to even years until benefits realisation supports what in literature is called the time lag of benefits realisation.

Code	Number	Percentage
1 – 6 months	11	25 %
6 – 12 months	9	20 %

Table 9: Time until benefits are realised

The respondents seeing benefits from the first day are all top managers, who probably want to justify the investment. The pessimistic answer seeing no benefit at all comes from company D as illustrated in fig. 5 and is a simple end user. The letters A – D identify the companies of the quantitative study as per table 1.

Figure 5: Time lag in the 4 companies of the quantitative study

The average value of the time lag until benefit is achieved for all four companies is 18.5 months. Fig. 5 shows, that some companies are more successful than others in realising benefits. Company A is the best one and company D has the worst implementation. Company A is the only, which applied the concept of benefit management from Ward. The other companies did not know benefit management and therefore did not use it. Respondents mention a stabilization phase in the first months. Another interesting finding is, that the benefits are realised differently in different applications.

Question 9: Would it be possible to reduce this time until benefit realisation and if yes, how?

25 % of the respondents say, it is not possible to reduce this time lag. It is noted that these respondents are the same who said, that the ERP-system delivered benefits from the first day.

Code	Number	Percentage
Intensive user training	20	46 %
Reduction of time lag nearly impossible	11	25 %

Table 10: Measures to reduce the time until benefits are realised

The other 75 % have various ideas. Surprisingly a very high percentage of 46 % votes for more end user training to benefit from the new ERP system. A detailed evaluation of the answers reveals plenty of plausible ideas to improve benefits realisation like redesigning business processes before the ERP implementation, providing more resources for the implementation project, more testing, applying change management, implementing a key user concept, improving the acceptance of the ERP system and putting more effort in the conception. The key user concept has proved as successful in practice in companies A and B, as it contributes to a know-how transfer from the project team to the end users acting as a multiplier. Furthermore, key users serve as primary contact for the end users and they can give trainings thanks to their good process knowledge.

Question 10: Which stakeholders can influence the benefits realisation in a positive way and if so, how?

The first part of the question covers, who are the stakeholders. The second part of the question is dedicated to the "how": how do stakeholders contribute to benefits realisation. 73 % of the interviewees consider the management board / top management as the most important stakeholder of an ERP implementation. This corresponds to the findings of Malik et al. [Malik, 25]. The top management has two functions, as shown in table 12. First it supports the implementation of the ERP system giving it a top priority and strategic importance and second, allocates the required funds and resources. Also a leadership backed innovation culture and investments in human capabilities support resilient performance during transformation [Bahyan, 25]. This makes sure that an ERP implementation is not just an IT project but a strategic project, where every employee is committed to cooperate. This explains why middle management and employees are mentioned also as stakeholders. Key users are quoted

again by 30 % of the interviewees as important stakeholders as shown under question 9. The middle management is quoted by 27 % of the persons for their duty to release employees from everyday work and allocate them to the implementation project.

Code	Number	Percentage
Management board, top management	32	73 %
Key users	13	30 %
Middle management	12	27 %
Employees	12	27 %

Table 11: Who are the stakeholders of benefits realisation

Code	Number	Percentage
Support of the ERP project	18	50 %
Allocate Resources	11	25 %

Table 12: How do stakeholders contribute to benefits realisation

Question 11: Which measures could improve the benefits of an ERP system in productive operation?

Productive operation starts with the going live marking the beginning of the postimplementation phase. Training of end users is quoted by 52 % of the interviewees. The reason for this demand is fluctuation of employees, new staff, insufficient training in the implementation project, forgetfulness and changes and new business processes, which call for regular trainings and refresh trainings. Training requirements are heavily neglected in practice, as some of the interviewed consultants said. Typically there is not enough budget left from the implementation project to be spent for trainings. Adapting business processes is done to optimize them but also completely new processes are implemented, e. g. for digitalization, sometimes because of regulatory or legal requirements. Technical updates of the ERP-system include IT related tasks like software updates, patches, release changes und installing add-ons. 46 % of the interviewed users point out the importance to maintain the ERP system to keep it up to date and to offer new functionalities. This code is mainly IT technical, whereas the next one, continuous improvement is related to eliminating errors, minor optimization activities and simplifications, master data maintenance and archiving of old data. Automation finally contributes to increase efficiency of the system by replacing manual activities by automatisms like workflows. Automation has considerable potential to leverage benefits of an ERP system.

Code	Number	Percentage
Training	23	52 %
Adapting business processes and new processes	21	48 %
Technical updates of the ERP system	20	46 %
Continuous improvement	17	39 %
Automation	15	34 %

Table 13: Measures to improve benefits in operation

Question 12: How can you recognize or quantify an improvement in benefits realisation in productive operation?

The highest percentage of 30 % is for “faster execution of processes”, which means shorter process times” and “time savings” for the individual users, as one respondent pointed out, that the MRP planning is faster, more accurate and avoids manual work. Finally the expected major benefit of an ERP system is to do the same work in less time resulting in higher efficiency. Further codes which are quoted, comprise user satisfaction (23 %), use of KPIs (23 %) and higher data quality (21 %). In many answers the same KPIs are mentioned as in question 5. This suggests to use the same set of KPIs over the complete life cycle of an ERP system, as described in chapter 5 of this paper.

Code	Number	Percentage
Faster execution of processes	13	30 %
Time savings for users	11	25 %

Table 14: Detecting benefits of an ERP system in productive operation

Summarizing the results of the qualitative research, which is the essence of more than 20 hours of audio recorded interviews, the idea that benefits can be measured and improved over time is supported by the following questions:

Question 4: KPIs are considered as a suitable instrument for measuring benefits.

Question 5: Specific KPIs are mentioned, including those of the quantitative study

Question 8: Recognising a time lag of many months until benefits realisation.

3.2 Quantitative Study

The results of the quantitative study will be presented in a separate paper. For this reason the focus here is on two selected examples of the 12 KPIs, namely average inventory value of raw materials and average lead time of customer orders.

They shall illustrate the time dependence of values for the KPIs, the initial performance dip immediately after going live and the differences of the four companies. In addition to the 24 monthly data points a regression curve is added, which is of third order. In the upper right corner of the diagram the R^2 is shown, which represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables, through a cubic polynomial equation. As the R^2 is higher than 0.95 the fit is pretty good. Data are from productive ERP systems of the four analysed companies A, B, C and D.

A linear regression line was intentionally not used to avoid the impression that things become better over time, which is not the case. From literature and the interviews we know that KPIs generally are bad after going live, improve over time until the end of the second year to become worse again. The regression curve of third order represents this very well.

3.2.1 Average Inventory value for raw materials

Fig. 6 shows the average of the inventory value for raw materials over a period of 24 months after going live for company A. A little increase in periods 2 and 3 can be seen. The inventory value is rather constant for the first 9 months before it drops to 60

% of its initial value after 18 months because of better processes in inventory management and more accurate material requirement planning.

Figure 6: Average inventory value over time for company A

Fig. 7 shows the data from company B. An increase by around 50 % can be seen in periods 3 and 4 before a lower level is reached in period 6. The sharp increase starting with period 12 has its origin in a company acquisition and is not caused by the ERP system.

Figure 7: Average inventory value over time for company B

For company C an increase in the first 5 periods can be seen in fig. 8, followed by periods of stronger standard deviations before the inventory values stay rather constant in the second year. Altogether no inventory reduction can be achieved.

Figure 8: Average inventory value over time for company C

For company D an increase in the first 5 periods can be seen in fig. 9, followed by 7 periods of constant inventory reduction. The curve shows the seasonal business of this company. A total inventory reduction between 15 - 20 % can be observed after 24 months.

Figure 9: Average inventory value over time for company D

3.2.2 Average lead time of customer orders

The second example shows the average lead time of customer orders.

Fig. 10 shows an initial reduction of the lead time in company A followed by a deterioration until the end of the first year and improvements in the second year at high standard deviations. The average lead time of 24 days in the first year is reduced to 15 days in the second year. This marks a reduction by 38 % in the second year with smoothly working business processes in the new ERP system.

Figure 10: Lead time of customer orders over time for company A

Fig. 11 shows the results for company B, which has difficulties with their deliveries in the first 5 months. In periods 6 to 18 lead time could be reduced by around 20 %.

Figure 11: Lead time of customer orders over time for company B

Fig. 12 shows the results for company C, which has difficulties with their deliveries in the second period caused by material shortages during the conversion from the old system to the ERP system. In periods 17 to 21 lead times are quite constant.

Figure 12: Lead time of customer orders over time for company C

Finally fig. 13 shows the results for company D, which has difficulties with their deliveries in periods 2 to 4 caused by material shortages during the conversion from the old system to the ERP system.

Figure 13: Lead time of customer orders over time for company D

Another proposed KPI is Ebit. The expectation is that an improved efficiency of business processes results in lower costs and finally in higher profits. But this cannot be verified based on the data of the companies. Many influence factors like market, takeover of other companies, structural changes, new products and customers have a strong impact on the Ebit. This is the reason that the improved efficiency thanks to the new ERP system cannot be discerned from the other influencing components of the Ebit. Another problem with this KPI is that two of the four companies were not willing to use and publish Ebit data in the quantitative study.

4 Synthesis of results

4.1 Contrasting quantitative and qualitative results

Finally the findings of the independently executed qualitative and quantitative study are combined and compared with each other.

KPIs are mentioned by 46 % of the interviewees in question four of the qualitative study. This is a good indication that the use of KPIs to measure the benefits of ERP systems is a viable way as done in the quantitative study. There is a good match between the KPIs proposed by the interview partners in question five of the qualitative study and the KPIs selected by the project leader of the ERP implementation project in company A in the quantitative study. A little difference is that general KPI inventory value in the qualitative study is split in inventory value for raw materials and finished products in the quantitative study. Persons involved in the qualitative and quantitative study are totally different and do not know the KPIs of the other study.

KPIs proposed in qualitative study	KPIs selected for quantitative study
Inventory value	Inventory value raw materials
Inventory value	Inventory value finished products
Inventory turnover	Inventory turnover raw materials
Inventory turnover	Inventory turnover finished products
Cycle time production orders	Cycle time production orders
Adherence to plan	Deviation actual costs – plan costs for production orders
Lead time customer orders	Lead time customer orders
Delivery reliability	Delivery reliability
Duration of period end closing	Number of days for period end closing
Number of IT tickets	Number of IT tickets
System usage	Number of active users of ERP system

Table 15: KPIs proposed in the qualitative and quantitative study

All KPIs measured in the quantitative study are also proposed in the qualitative study. In addition, another 29 KPIs are cited in question 5 of the qualitative study, like number of posted documents per user of the ERP system and data quality and customer satisfaction, which are difficult to measure.

In question 6 of the qualitative study most respondents agree to a periodic measurement of the KPIs on a yearly basis. In the quantitative study a monthly

measurement of the KPIs is applied to detect, if there is a time dependency in the initial time after going live. For the future measurement of benefits realisation an interval of 6 or 12 months might be sufficient.

In question 8 of the qualitative study 16 % of the interviewed persons estimate a time lag of six months until benefits are realised compared to the old legacy system. Another 16 % believe, that the time lag is two years and further 11 % expect one to two years. Generally, the majority of ERP users expect an improvement of benefits over time. This corresponds with the diagrams of selected KPIs versus time in chapter 3.2 showing an improvement of KPIs in the quantitative study for company A. It should be mentioned that the values for benefits realisation are pretty good, as the principle of benefit management is applied for the implementation of the ERP system [Ward, 06]. In other organisations the benefits may be realised slower or to a smaller extent.

In other words, the diagrams may look different for different KPIs in different organisations. The diagrams will not always show an improvement of a KPI. It is possible that a deterioration occurs, because know-how and experience is lost in case of fluctuation of employees. A common pattern is an improvement of a KPI several months after going live, which is partly lost two or more years later, when continuous improvement of an ERP system and benefits realisation is neglected. Examples are the customer order lead time in company B and statements from interviewed consultants saying that KPIs can deteriorate over time because of fluctuation of personal and neglected training of users.

Answers for question 4 regarding quantifying the benefits and question twelve regarding quantifying the increases of benefits after continuous improvement show a strong correlation of the answers. A quantification of benefits can be done by means of the same KPIs for the initial measurement of benefits and for going on measurements for the continuous improvement of the ERP system and the business processes. So it seems feasible to develop a concept of benefit controlling, as explained in chapter five.

4.2 Contrasting empirical results and theory

The results of the studies are in line with the existing literature. Some findings shall be highlighted here.

The IS success model developed by DeLone/McLean is mentioned here, as in some interviews the positive correlation between intensity of usage and benefit of the ERP system is mentioned [DeLone, 03]. The variables “intention to use the system” and “user satisfaction” are self-reinforcing and both have a positive impact on net benefits.

Figure 14: IS success model (DeLone/McLean)

The first insight is, that the generic IS success model is applicable also for ERP systems. Based on this the second insight is that it is important to motivate users to use the system and to care for a high user satisfaction.

Next the Benefit Management developed by Ward is contrasted with the present research [Ward, 96]. Published in 1996 it could not reach practical relevance despite the fact that the PRINCE2 framework requires the use of Benefit Management for public projects in UK. None of the interviewed persons knows the concept of Benefit Management except the project manager of company A in the quantitative study, who applied basic principles of Benefit Management for the ERP implementation. Comparing the KPIs of the participating companies A, B, C and D shows that company A has a good benefits realisation. This is supported by the perceived time lags of these four companies shown in figure 5. This is an indication that applying the concept of Benefit Management is worthwhile.

Ifinedo et al. state a lack of research in the postimplementation phase of ERP systems and suggest longitudinal studies to research the success of ERP systems over the entire life cycle [Ifinedo, 10]. Badewi writes “a longitudinal study is advised, ... to see how the benefits are realised” [Badewi, 16]. Cotteleer/Bendoly come to the conclusion that “longitudinal approaches could open doors to practice and new theory that are difficult to anticipate based on current knowledge” [Cotteleer, 06], as the own quantitative study demonstrates.

In question 3 of the qualitative study (detecting benefits) the answers “increase of efficiency”, “faster business processes” and “decision support” match with the main type of benefits evaluated by Bernroider “business process improvement”, “reduced cycle times” and “enhanced decision making” [Bernroider, 08].

In question 7 of the qualitative study (external influence factors reflected by the KPIs) 18 % mention qualification of employees and 9 % fluctuation of employees. Markus/Tanis state that the loss of know-how because of fluctuation of employees as a problem [Markus, 00] like Ashurst/Hodges do [Ashurst, 10].

Regarding question 8 of the qualitative study (time until benefits are realised) the results are comparable to the IPO-model of Zwikael/Smyrk mentioning a duration in the order of several months up to years until full benefit is realised [Zwikael, 09].

In question 9 of the qualitative study 23 % of the interviewees cite the improvement of business processes as one measure to reduce the time until benefits are realised. Muschter emphasizes the importance of a continued improvement of business processes to leverage benefits [Muschter, 99]. Bernroider/Leseure mention the strategic importance of business process reengineering and business process improvement [Bernroider, 05].

In question 10 of the qualitative study 73 % of the interviewees cite the top management as a key stakeholder, as its commitment is crucial for the project success. This is in line with statements of Weill [Weill, 92], Ward/Daniel [Ward, 12], Chih/Zwikael [Chih, 15] and Sumner [Sumner, 18].

One of the main ideas of the own quantitative study is to use time series data extracted directly from an ERP system ex post to avoid that a longitudinal study over 24 months will last 24 months. The long time required is probably one reason that only few longitudinal studies can be found in literature. The idea of an ex post study may sound simple, but require SAP-expertise to extract the data, as there are no standard reports for some of the KPIs. Regarding data from an ERP-system Muschter/Österle also argue that objectively measured data is preferable to manually acquired data because of less work for data acquisition and cleansing and less risk of data manipulation [Muschter, Österle, 99].

One comparative example from the quantitative study and literature is the reduction of the value of inventory. Martin/Mauterer/Gemünden describe two cases with a reduction of inventory values by 29 % and 30 % over three years [Martin, 02]. This is of a similar order like the reduction of the inventory of raw materials by 50 % and of finished goods by 23 % after two years in company A. However, a reduction of inventory values is not always achieved, as the case of company B shows.

5 Concept of benefit controlling

As the KPIs from the four companies show a distinct time dependence, the author proposes an integrated benefit controlling to monitor the benefits realisation based on a set of selected KPIs over the life time of an ERP system. For this purpose process KPIs like customer order lead time and other KPIs from the quantitative study can be used. These KPIs to monitor the benefits realisation are other KPIs, which are used for corporate reporting such as Ebit, ROCE, etc. External effects like economy, material shortages on the supply side must be eliminated to focus just on the improvements

coming from the ERP system. This is a further development of the periodic benefit reviews proposed by Tallon/Kraemer/Gurbaxani [Tallon, 00].

Figure 15: Concept of benefit controlling

Based on the actual value of a KPI in the legacy system, which marks the benefit level of the old system a planned benefit level is defined as target for the new ERP system (shown in red colour in the above figure). The actual values of the respective KPI shall be measured on a half yearly or yearly basis (shown as green dots on the blue curve in the above figure) to see to which extent benefits have been realised. Plan values shall be defined before planned discontinuities such as digitalization measures, release changes, redesign of business processes or implementation of new functionalities. One practical example is the legally required implementation of e-invoicing, which speeds up invoice processing by eliminating manual process steps like printing or mailing.

The author proposes an annual review of the actual key figures by the process owners in the sense of a controlling process to see if benefits realisation leads to an improvement or deterioration of KPIs.

This concept contributes to the literature, as existing literature mainly focuses on a review of the implementation project based on costs, time and scope. According to Ward 81 % of interviewed persons are not satisfied with the practices in their organizations to evaluate benefits [Ward, 07].

6 Conclusions

The first result is that the question regarding the measurability of benefits can be answered with yes. The qualitative study shows that the majority of the interviewed users and consultants are of the opinion that benefits can be measured based on different KPIs and that it takes some time until benefits are realised.

The second result from the evaluation of KPIs in the quantitative study is that time dependency and especially the performance dip after going live could be demonstrated based on 12 KPIs (inventory value of raw materials, stock turnover rate of raw materials, cycle time of production orders, cost deviation of production orders, inventory value of finished goods, stock turnover rate of finished goods, lead time of customer orders, delivery reliability, percentage of customer orders delivered in time, duration of monthly financial closing, number of IT tickets and system usage). There is no other study worldwide comprising so many KPIs. Known studies are limited mostly to one single KPI like order lead time.

The third result is the concept of a benefit controlling for the postimplementation phase, which shall support the process of benefits realisation of the ERP system's lifetime.

7 Future Work

It is proposed to conduct future research in the following four areas.

First in the refinement of the KPI system to find out, which KPIs are most suitable for tracking the benefits realisation.

Second a replication of the study to the new generation of SAP software, S/4HANA, which replaces SAP ERP used in this study.

Third the benefits realisation of cloud-based ERP-systems, which might have a quicker benefits realisation due to preconfigured best practice processes.

And finally, the application of the benefit controlling to projects of digitalization, as this also is related to changes in business processes like in case of ERP-systems, where a fast benefits realisation is crucial.

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References

[Ashurst, 10] Ashurst, C.; Hodges, J.: Exploring business transformation: The challenges of developing a benefits realization capability, in: *Journal of Change Management*, Vol. 10, No. 2, 2010, 217-237.

[Atkinson, 99] Atkinson, R.: Project management: cost, time and quality, two best guesses and a phenomenon, its time to accept other success criteria, in: *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 17, No. 6, 1999, 337-342.

[Badewi, 16] Badewi, A.: The impact of project management (PM) and benefits management (BM) practices on project success: Towards developing a project benefits governance framework, in: *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 34, No. 4, 2016, 761-778.

- [Bahyan, 25] Bahyan, H., Ajmal, M. M., Saber, H.: Going resilient with digital transformation, human capabilities and innovation readiness: Empirical evidence from the energy sector, in: *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, Vol. 32, No. 5, 2025, 1522–1540.
- [Bernroider, 05] Bernroider, E.; Leseure, M.: Enterprise resource planning (ERP) diffusion and characteristics according to the system's lifecycle. A comparative view of small-to-medium sized and large enterprises, Working paper, Vienna University of Economics and Business Administration, 2005.
- [Bernroider, 08] Bernroider, E.: IT governance for enterprise resource planning supported by the DeLone–McLean model of information systems success, in: *Information & Management*, Vol. 45, No. 5, 2008, 257-269.
- [Chih, 15] Chih, Y.; Zwikael, O.: Project benefit management: A conceptual framework of target benefit formulation, in: *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 2015, 352-362.
- [Coombs, 14] Coombs, C.: When planned IS/IT project benefits are not realized: a study of inhibitors and facilitators to benefits realization, *International Journal of Project Management*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 2015, 363-379.
- [Cotteleer, 06] Cotteleer, M.; Bendoly, E.: Order lead-time improvement following enterprise information technology implementation: an empirical study, in: *MIS quarterly*, Vol. 30, No. 3, 2006, 643-660.
- [DeLone, 03] DeLone, W.; McLean, E.: The DeLone and McLean model of information systems success: a ten-year update, in: *Journal of management information systems*, Vol. 19, No. 4, 2003, 9-30.
- [Ifinedo, 10] Ifinedo, P.; Rapp, B.; Ifinedo, A.; Sundberg, K.: Relationships among ERP post-implementation success constructs: An analysis at the organizational level, in: *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 26, 2010, 1136-1148.
- [Malik, 25] Malik, M., Raziq, M.M., Sarwar, N., Tariq, A. (2025). Digital leadership, business model innovation and organizational change: role of leader in steering digital transformation, in: *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, Vol. 32, No. 2, 2025, 550-577.
- [Markus, 00] Markus, L.; Tanis, C.: The enterprise systems experience-from adoption to success, in: *Framing the domains of IT research: Glimpsing the future through the past*, Vol. 173, 2000, 173-207.
- [Martin, 02] Martin, R., Mauterer, H., Gemünden, H.: Systematisierung des Nutzens von ERP-Systemen in der Fertigungsindustrie, in: *Wirtschaftsinformatik*, Vol. 44., No. 2, 2002, 109-116.
- [McAfee, 02] McAfee, A.: The impact of enterprise information technology adoption on operational performance: An empirical investigation, in: *Production and operations management*, Vol. 11, No. 1, 2002, 33-53.
- [Muschter, 99] Muschter, S.: *IS-gestütztes Prozessmanagement*, Thesis, St. Gallen, 1999.
- [Muschter, Österle, 99] Muschter, S.; Österle, H.: Investitionen in Standardsoftware: Ein geschäftsorientierter Ansatz zur Nutzenmessung und -bewertung, in: *Electronic business engineering*, Physica-Verlag HD, 1999, 443-468.
- [Nelson, 07] Nelson, R.: IT Project Management: Infamous Failures, Classic Mistakes, and Best Practices, *MIS Quarterly Executives*, Vol. 6, No. 2, 2007, 67-78.
- [Schryen, 10] Schryen, G.: Ökonomischer Wert von Informationssystemen, in: *Wirtschaftsinformatik*, No. 4, 2010, 225-237.

- [Shang, 02] Shang, S., Seddon, P.: Assessing and managing the benefits of enterprise systems: the business manager's perspective, in: *Information systems journal*, Vol. 12, No. 4, 2002, 271-299.
- [Shang, 04] Shang, S., Seddon, P.: Enterprise Systems Benefits: How should they be assessed? *Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems Proceedings 2004*, 2004, 1229-1240.
- [Sumner, 18] Sumner, M.: ERP Project Retrospectives—55 Enterprise Systems: Evaluating Project Success, Lessons Learned, and Business Outcomes, *Proceedings MWAIS 2018*, Midwest Association for Information Systems, 2018, 12-23.
- [Tallon, 00] Tallon, P.; Kraemer, K.; Gurbaxani, V.: Executives' perceptions of the business value of information technology: a process-oriented approach, in: *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 16, No. 4, 2000, 145-173.
- [Ward, 96] Ward, J.; Taylor, P.; Bond, P.: Evaluation and realisation of IS/IT benefits: an empirical study of current practice, in: *European Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 4, No. 4, 1996, 214-225.
- [Ward, 06] Ward, J.; Daniel, E.: *Benefits Management: Delivering Value from IS/IT Investments*, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, 2006.
- [Ward, 07] Ward, J.; de Hertogh, S.; Viaene, S.: Managing Benefits from IS/IT Investments: an Empirical Investigation into Current Practice, *Proceedings of the 40th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 2007.
- [Ward, 12] Ward, J.; Daniel, E.: *Benefits Management: How to increase the business value of your IT projects*, John Wiley and Sons, 2nd edition, Chichester, 2012.
- [Weill, 92] Weill, P.: The Relationship between Investment in Information Technology and Firm Performance: A Study of the Valve Manufacturing Sector, in: *Information Systems Review*, Vol. 3, No. 4, 1992, 307-333.
- [Yin, 09] YIN, R.: *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*, 4th edition, Los Angeles, 2009.
- [Zwikael, 09] Zwikael, O.; Smyrk, J.: Towards an Outcome Based Project Management Theory, in: *2009 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management*, 2009, 633-637.